

Emerging Jets at Neutrinos and Charged Leptons High-Energy Beams

Borrello, Costa, Redigolo [2507.12527]

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Neutrino Masses: SeeSaw Framework

Standard seesaw

$$\mathcal{L} = y\bar{L}NH + \frac{1}{2}M\bar{N}^cN + \text{h.c.}$$

N SM singlet

active - sterile mixing

$$|U|^2 = \left(\frac{yv}{M}\right)^2 = \frac{m_\nu}{M}$$

Poor phenomenology: small mixing

SHiP collaboration [1811.00930v3]

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Inverse seesaw

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N, S SM singlets [Mohapatra and Valle, Phys. Rev. Lett. 44, 912 \(1980\)](#)

μ Majorana mass

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$$|U|^2 = \left(\frac{yv}{M}\right)^2 = \frac{m_\nu}{\mu}$$

μ is very small \implies Richer phenomenology

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Strongly coupled Dark Sectors

$$\mathcal{L} = y \bar{L} N H$$

Single particle state

What if N is an excitation of a strongly coupled DS?

$$\Delta \mathcal{L}_{5/2} = \frac{y_\mu \tilde{H} L \mathcal{O}_N}{\Lambda_{UV}^{\Delta_N - 3/2}}$$

Chacko et al. [2012.01443]

Composite operator of dimension Δ_N

$$\text{Dark baryon } \Delta_N = \frac{3}{2} \times 3 = 9/2$$

DS: 2 scales $\Lambda_{IR} \ll \Lambda_{UV} \rightarrow$ approximate CFT

Low energy theory of single particle states

$$\mathcal{O}_N \sim \Lambda_{IR}^{\Delta_N - 3/2} \psi$$

Scale of CFT deformations

e.g.: Interactions with SM

Strongly Coupled Sectors: Phenomenology

$$\Delta\mathcal{L}_{5/2} = \frac{y_\mu \tilde{H} L \mathcal{O}_N}{\Lambda_{UV}^{\Delta_N - 3/2}}$$

QCD-like phenomenology

Many Portals

$$\Delta_{\text{SM}} = 5/2$$

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Unique Opportunity to Test Effective Interactions

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} \supset \frac{O_{\text{SM}} O_{\text{NP}}}{\Lambda_{\text{UV}}^{D-4}}$$

Higher dimension $D > 5 \rightarrow$ signal increases with energy

$$s = 2m_p \bar{E}_\nu$$

$$\sigma \sim \frac{1}{s} \left(\frac{s}{\Lambda_{\text{UV}}^2} \right)^{D-4}$$

Unique opportunity: soon available neutrino beam with high energy and intensity

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Weak bosons and SM Higgs branching ratios

Neutrino disintegration at neutrino beams

Production at lepton/hadron colliders

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Lifetime of Light States

$$\Delta\mathcal{L}_{5/2} = \frac{y_\mu \tilde{H} L \mathcal{O}_N}{\Lambda_{UV}^{\Delta_N - 3/2}}$$

$$\Gamma_{HL} \sim \frac{\Lambda_{IR}^3}{64\pi^3} \left(\frac{C_{HL}}{v}\right)^2 \left(\frac{\Lambda_{IR}^2}{\Lambda_{UV}^2}\right)^{\Delta_N - 3/2}$$

Exploring emerging SM jet signatures:

Charged leptons + Missing energy

Primary vertex:
hadronic activity

Semi-leptonic

W branching ratios + kinematics
+ Z mediated decays

Emerging dark jets

Hadronic activity (primary vertex) + displaced jet of SM particles

Probability of decaying inside the detector

$$S_{\text{emerging}} \sim \underbrace{\frac{N_\nu}{\sigma_t} \frac{s^2}{\Lambda_{\text{UV}}^4 v^2} \left(\frac{s}{\Lambda_{\text{UV}}^2} \right)^{\Delta_N - 7/2}}_{\text{Production of DS jet}} \underbrace{\frac{L_{\text{det}}}{\gamma\beta c\tau} n_{\text{fragments}}}_{\text{Probability of decaying inside the detector}} \sim 1$$

Production of DS jet

Looking for unstable light states

Interesting signals with both theoretical and experimental challenges!

Challenges

- Minimum energy to identify the **primary vertex**
- Minimum observable **displacement**
- Trigger threshold in amount of **missing energy** in the SM emerging jet
- Minimum **energy in SM jet**
- Emerging jet of SM particles displaced from hadronic activity...backgrounds?

Summary

$$\Delta\mathcal{L}_{5/2} = \frac{y_\mu \tilde{H} L \mathcal{O}_N}{\Lambda_{UV}^{\Delta_N - 3/2}}$$

- **Emerging jets** leading probe of heavy (\rightarrow unstable) IR states
- Stable states tested through precision SM measures (**Higgs BR**) and **enhancement in neutral current**

Thank you for your attention and stay tuned!

Neutrino Masses and Compositeness

$$\mathcal{O}_N \sim \Lambda_{\text{IR}}^{\Delta_N - 3/2} \psi$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{UV}} = \frac{\tilde{H} L \mathcal{O}_N}{\Lambda_{\text{UV}}^{\Delta_N - 3/2}} + \mu \frac{\tilde{\mathcal{O}}}{\Lambda_{\text{UV}}^{\tilde{\Delta} - 4}}$$

Inverse seesaw in the IR

$\tilde{\mathcal{O}}$ lepton number violating deformation

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{IR}} \sim \left(\frac{\Lambda_{\text{IR}}}{\Lambda_{\text{UV}}} \right)^{\Delta_N - 3/2} H L \psi + \Lambda_{\text{IR}} \bar{\psi} \psi + \mu \Lambda_{\text{IR}} \left(\frac{\Lambda_{\text{IR}}}{\Lambda_{\text{UV}}} \right)^{\tilde{\Delta} - 4} \psi^2$$

Compositeness as explanation for small m_ν

$$m_\nu \sim \Lambda_{\text{IR}} \left[\left(\frac{v}{\Lambda_{\text{IR}}} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\Lambda_{\text{IR}}}{\Lambda_{\text{UV}}} \right)^{2\Delta_N - 3} \right] \left[\mu \left(\frac{\Lambda_{\text{IR}}}{\Lambda_{\text{UV}}} \right)^{\tilde{\Delta} - 4} \right]$$

$$\theta_{\nu\psi} \sim \frac{v}{\Lambda_{\text{IR}}} \left(\frac{\Lambda_{\text{IR}}}{\Lambda_{\text{UV}}} \right)^{\Delta_N - 3/2}$$

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Small lepton number violation in the composite sector

Compositeness as explanation for small m_ν

Small elementary-composite mixing

$$m_\nu \sim \Lambda_{\text{IR}} \left[\left(\frac{v}{\Lambda_{\text{IR}}} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\Lambda_{\text{IR}}}{\Lambda_{\text{UV}}} \right)^{2\Delta_N - 3} \right] \left[\mu \left(\frac{\Lambda_{\text{IR}}}{\Lambda_{\text{UV}}} \right)^{\tilde{\Delta} - 4} \right]$$

$$\theta_{\nu\psi} \sim \frac{v}{\Lambda_{\text{IR}}} \left(\frac{\Lambda_{\text{IR}}}{\Lambda_{\text{UV}}} \right)^{\Delta_N - 3/2}$$

Computing Inclusive Rates

n state in the continuum

Optical theorem

$$\sum_n \int d\Phi_n^{DS} |\langle \Omega | \mathcal{O}_{DS} | n \rangle|^2 = 2\text{Im} (i \langle \Omega | \mathcal{O}_{DS}(p_{DS}) \mathcal{O}_{DS}(-p_{DS}) | \Omega \rangle)$$

2pt function: fixed by symmetry

Scalar operator

$$\text{Im}(i \langle T \mathcal{O}_S(-p) \mathcal{O}_S(p) \rangle) = c_{\mathcal{O}_S} \frac{\pi(\Delta_S - 1)}{\Gamma(\Delta_S)^2 4^{\Delta_S - 1}} (p^2)^{\Delta_S - 2}$$

Fermion operator

$$\text{Im}(i \langle T \mathcal{O}_N(-p) \bar{\mathcal{O}}_N(p) \rangle) = \not{p} \frac{c_N 2^{3-2\Delta_N} \pi}{\Gamma(\Delta_N - 3/2) \Gamma(\Delta_N + 1/2)} (p^2)^{\Delta_N - 5/2}$$

Energy Dependent R^ν

Reminder: with SM ElectroWeak Interactions

$$R^\nu \equiv \frac{\sigma(\nu_\mu N \rightarrow \nu_\mu X)}{\sigma(\nu_\mu N \rightarrow \mu^- X)} = \frac{\sigma_{NC}^\nu}{\sigma_{CC}^\nu} = g_L^2 + r g_R^2 \quad \text{SM cross-sections} \propto s \implies R^\nu \text{ constant with } s$$

DS: energy dependent enhancement of NC/CC

$$\sigma_{HL} \sim \frac{C_{HL}^2}{v^2} \left(\frac{s}{\Lambda_{UV}^2} \right)^{\Delta_N - 3/2} \quad R_\nu(s) \equiv \frac{\sigma(\nu N \rightarrow \nu X)}{\sigma(\nu N \rightarrow \mu^- X)} = g_L^2 + r g_R^2 + \Delta g^2(s)$$

For monochromatic beam @ \bar{s}

$$\frac{\text{BSM NC}'_s}{\text{SM CC}'_s} \sim \frac{\bar{s} v^2}{\Lambda_{UV}^4} \left(\frac{\bar{s}}{\Lambda_{UV}^2} \right)^{\Delta_N - \frac{7}{2}}$$

Inclusive Dark Jets at Neutrino Beams

Not looking for ψ decays: only hadronic activity \rightarrow background from SM neutral current

$$\sigma_Q = \int_{4\Lambda_{\text{IR}}^2}^s dm_D^2 \int dx dy \frac{d^3\sigma}{dx dy dm_D^2} \times f_q(x, Q^2) \quad \frac{d\sigma_Q}{dm_D^2} \sim \frac{y_\mu^2}{8\pi^2 \Lambda_{\text{UV}}^4 v^2} \left(\frac{m_D^2}{\Lambda_{\text{UV}}^2} \right)^{\Delta_N - 7/2} (s - m_D^2)$$

If **UV dominated** (continuum production dominant)

$$\sigma_{HL} \sim \frac{C_{HL}^2}{v^2} \left(\frac{s}{\Lambda_{\text{UV}}^2} \right)^{\Delta_N - 3/2}$$

Preferred higher energy experiment and scattering over nucleons